

EXPLANATION OF IDIOMS AND THEIR ROLE IN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. Overall, this article illustrates information about idioms in Uzbek and English language. In addition, this article might be useful for linguists and students as well. The reason is, there will be given many information about idioms and their beneficial sides for educational fields. After reading this article, learners and others may know how to use idioms in their everyday life as well as through communication. Therefore, idioms can be helpful for language skills. Not because, it can make your speech more colorful, but because you can learn how to speak and interact like natives.

Key words: Knowledge, translate, show up, various, programs, fluent.

Аннотация. В целом, эта статья содержит информацию об идиомах в узбекском и английском языках. Кроме того, она может быть полезна лингвистам и студентам. В ней представлено много информации об идиомах и их пользе для образования. Прочитав эту статью, учащиеся и другие люди смогут узнать, как использовать идиомы в повседневной жизни, а также в общении. Таким образом, идиомы могут быть полезны для развития языковых навыков. Не потому, что они могут сделать вашу речь более выразительной, а потому, что вы можете научиться говорить и общаться как носители языка.

Ключевые слова: Знание, переводить, показывать, различные, программы, беглый.

Annotatsiya. Umuman olganda, ushbu maqola o'zbek va ingliz tillarida idiomalar haqida ma'lumot beradi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola tilshunoslar va talabalar uchun ham foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Sababi, iboralar va ularning ta'lim sohalari uchun foydali tomonlari haqida ko'plab ma'lumotlar beriladi. Ushbu maqolani o'qib chiqqandan so'ng, o'quvchilar va boshqalar o'zlarining kundalik hayotida, shuningdek, muloqot orqali idiomalardan qanday foydalanishni bilishlari mumkin. Shuning uchun idiomalar til ko'nikmalari uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Bu maqola sizning nutqingizni yanada rang-barang qilishi uchun emas, balki siz mahalliy aholi kabi gapirish va muloqot qilishni o'rganishingiz uchun kerakli ma'lumotlarni jamlagan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bilim, tarjima, o'zini ko'rsatish, turli xil, programma, ravon.

Learning a new language is very interesting and fun for everyone. The reason is, while you are learning a foreign language, you will become close to that nation's traditions and customs. In addition, you can broaden your horizon. Because, when you interact with others and share your personal ideas, you can also change your opinions and ideas into the positive way. So, it is recommended that everyone should learn other languages for themselves.

When we compare people's opinion and outlooks with language learners and non-language learners, you can see a huge difference between them. Individuals who can speak through a number of languages can express their ideas without any challenges and mistakes.

Because, learning an unfamiliar language can help you to gain more knowledge and other essential methods.

However, people who cannot communicate by another language might have some difficulties while expressing their ideas. Thus, it would be effective way for every individual to learn a new language.

Learning an English language and how to speak it can definitely change your life.

Because, English traditions are very modern and might change your thoughts into positive way. If you want to enter the University that is located in the USA, you can achieve high academic performances.

Their strategies and educational techniques are on a high position compared with other countries. However, there are other countries as well that you can study there, such as Germany, Korea, Japan and UK. If you choose to study in those countries, you can meet highly skilled and well-educated tutors and professors. But, you have to have some basic and initial knowledge and explanation about English and how to speak at least B2 level to enter that Academic campuses.

You will be examined beforehand or you have to have certificate named IELTS at least 6.5 or 7.0. Taking this certificate can change your life in a good way. It can open many doors for you.

You can study and work with the help of this certificate. So, idioms can help you to get high score from this IELTS examination. Idioms are often used by native speakers in their daily life. On top that, if you watch English movies and cartoons, you might hear idioms. Thus, if you use Idioms in your exam day of writing and Speaking section correctly, you can get high scores.

The origin and history of idioms came from each nation's history and tradition. There are a lot of idioms that has been using through many decades in each country. Idioms cannot be introduced in a short period of time. It can be appeared by each population's traditions and cultures.

Therefore, if you translate Uzbek idioms into English, it might be difficult to find reliable translation and explanation of idioms. But, hardly ever there might be some same idioms in both languages. If you are a linguist and give incorrect explanation, learners might understand and realize that idioms with mistake. So, it is believed that idioms are a part of each language and population. It can help you to become successful in your field.

Here are some idioms in English with examples and explanation.

1. **“Turn a blind eye”** means to refuse to acknowledge a known truth.

Example: My mother always turn a blind eye when I do something bad that cannot be corrected.

There are many given meanings for this word by writers and linguists. However, Horatio Nelson's explanation is accepted widely. In 1801, he managed the battle of Copenhagen with Admiral Sir Hyde Parker. Nelson was blind in one eye. Parker communicated to Nelson at one point, via flags, that he needed to retreat and disengage. However, Nelson was sure that if they kept moving forward, they could win. Then he put the telescope to his blind eye and acted as if he didn't see the signal. He jokingly told his fellow officer that he wanted to keep the right to use his “blind eye” sometimes. And so, idiom of “turn a blind eye” introduced to linguistic sphere.

2. **“Feeling under the weather”** means to feel ill.

Example: I think I cannot go to the conference, because I'm feeling a bit under the weather.

It is believed that this idiom is belong to nature. The reason is, there was a man in the history. He was a sailor. When he felt ill, he went beneath the bow which is the front part of the boat.

This would probably protect him from adverse conditions, as he was a literally under the bad weather that could further sicken him. Therefore, a sailor who was sick could be described as being “feeling under the weather”.

There are a lot of information, books and articles related to idioms on websites. You can easily find related materials at any time and everywhere. Learning idioms will be very essential for communication, if you go to another country. The reason is, native speakers use from idiomatic language all the time. Therefore, you should gain knowledge about idioms. You don't need someone who should taught you idioms.

You can use through related programs, online and video lessons or even reading books.

However, learning idioms isn't easy process as you thought. You cannot translate them directly word by word. You should understand the overall meaning of them.

Let's learn by looking at example.

Example: “Someone is a big fish”. It doesn't mean that someone is a big fish, it means someone is being the leader or the boss.

Example: “Kill two birds with one stone”. It means to accomplish two different things at the same time, it doesn't mean killing birds.

If you want to speak fluently, you should know how to use idioms correctly. Because, meaning of it is differ from original form as I mentioned early. Firstly, you shouldn't make grammar mistakes and you should put and use them in your sentence without mistakes. Then, you should pronounce them correctly. After that, idioms can make your speech more beautiful than before as it has a number of advantages sides. First of all, your audience, partner or listener can understand you smoothly which can make your speech perfect if you use correctly.

Secondly, you can show up your knowledge by using idiomatic language because it is very difficult for non-native speakers to use idioms in their speech and everyday conversation.

Nowadays, learning new language is being popular among both young and old generation.

What I mean by that, learning foreign language can give you a number of productive opportunities for your career, profession and other alternatives. If you want to enter university, go abroad to study or want to work, you absolutely need to speak different languages especially English. If you are a teacher, you should have an international certificate that can show your knowledge on one language like Russian, Arabic or the most famous one English. By this certificate you can get a high salary. On top of that, you don't have a chance work at schools, universities and other fields that related to education. The reason is, as a teacher you must have an ability to educate all students with high requirements.

At these days, there are a huge number of teachers that are not good at with their jobs.

Therefore, having an IELTS, TESOL, TOEFL and other certificates are required in education workplaces. For that, you should have a strong knowledge for speaking, writing, listening and reading. You can boost your reading knowledge by reading books and articles. For listening you should listen and watch podcasts and movies with close attention. When it comes to speaking and writing. You should use idiomatic language to get a desired band score. Using idioms can give you a chance to get 7+ both in speaking and writing but without grammar and pronunciation mistakes. It doesn't mean that you should use many idioms in your speech and essay.

You can use some of them where needed and reliable.

-Recommendations for students who want to use idioms in Speaking section:

1. You can search idiom through videos on YouTube, internet, books and articles. I give my valuable advice for students who want to boost their speaking score by using idioms. They can find idioms by watching podcasts on YouTube or movies. Additionally, reading books can also help them to find idiom. It is also beneficial for reading ability like comprehension.

2. Learn idioms by meaning. After they have found idioms, they should translate them by using dictionary or online platforms in order to know their meaning and write them in your notebook.

3. Use programs to help you translating meaning of idioms. There are a number of AI programs that can help you to translate idiom's meaning. You can use ChatGpt.

4. Make up sentence with idioms. After you have done all the steps that I mentioned, you should use them in your speech. Without practice you cannot learn idioms.

The recommendations I gave you for speaking is also suitable for writing too.

I hope I could give you useful information about idioms.

Wish you good luck with your study!

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